

Transcription Guidelines (2025)

Taxonomy, Language-Specific Features, and Positioning in Research & Practice

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Abstract

Transcription exists on a spectrum between readability and level of detail. These guidelines define three Amberscript **transcription types** – **Clean Read (CR)**, **Clean Verbatim (CV)** and **Full Verbatim (FV)** – and standardise their operations at the lexical, syntactic and paralinguistic level. The primary focus of this document is English (EN). Notes on DE/NL/FR are included as optional examples. A conservative tagging and timestamp policy ($\leq 1/\text{min}$; thresholds $\text{CR/CV} \geq 5 \text{ s}$, $\text{FV} \geq 3 \text{ s}$) increases reproducibility and tool interoperability. Examples (trptychs) illustrate transformations from the spoken utterance to CR/CV/FV. The result: citable, auditable and cross-linguistically consistent transcripts for research and practice.

Keywords

Transcription; **Clean Read**; **Clean Verbatim**; **Full Verbatim**; TEI P5; ISO 24624; Jefferson; GAT2; EN/DE/NL/FR; timestamps; backchannels; reproducibility

1. Introduction: problem statement, aim, contribution, scope

Problem statement

Transcription is not a monolithic process but a continuum between fidelity to content and readability. Research domains (e.g. linguistics, sociology, discourse analysis) require high granularity and formally marked phenomena, while practice-oriented fields (journalism, UX, knowledge management) need low friction and high reading flow. Without clearly defined styles, divergences emerge between transcripts, which can distort research results: inconsistent tag usage, unclear distinctions (e.g. disfluencies vs. filler words), inconsistent punctuation, and limited compatibility with established research standards (TEI P5, ISO 24624).

Aim

To provide a versioned, stably citable reference for the Amberscript styles **Clean Read (CR)**, **Clean Verbatim (CV)** and **Full Verbatim (FV)**. The guidelines define:

- Tagging/timestamp norms,
- language-specific defaults with a focus on DE (optional short references: EN, NL, FR),
- mappings to other relevant research standards.

Contribution

- A consolidated taxonomy with clear operations at the lexical, syntactic and paralinguistic levels.
- Unified terminology and norms, including:
 - **Per-minute timestamp rule:** ≤ 1 per minute (per speaker turn).
 - **Duration thresholds:** CR/CV ≥ 5 s, FV ≥ 3 s (see Section 3 for language-specific deviations).
 - Tags in lower case, in square brackets; canonical English labels with permitted language-local aliases (a transcript chooses one variant and uses it consistently, with local aliases recommended to improve accessibility).
- A normative framework with **MUST/SHOULD/MAY** to increase reproducibility (inter-annotator agreement), tool compatibility, and citability.

Scope

These guidelines address transcription styles. Subtitle-specific aspects (SDH/accessibility typography) are explicitly excluded.

Versioning/citation

This document is versioned (current version v2025.11-1).

1.1 Responsibility of transcribers (professionalism, precision, confidentiality)

Purpose. This chapter defines minimum standards for the professional practice of transcription work in order to ensure quality, reproducibility, and confidentiality.

Principles (MUST/SHOULD/MAY)

Precision & consistency

- Transcribers **MUST** apply the style- and language-specific rules of these guidelines strictly (**CR/CV/FV** operations; micro-typography; number/time formats; tag policy).
- They **MUST** use tags in a uniform way: lower case, in square brackets, and remain consistent within a transcript (canonical EN forms, optional language-local aliases).
- They **MUST** comply with the per-minute timestamp rule (≤ 1 per minute per speaker turn) and the duration thresholds ($CR/CV \geq 5$ s; $FV \geq 3$ s).
- They **SHOULD** mark uncertainties transparently (e.g. [inaudible], [unclear] with an optional time range, depending on transcription style) instead of guessing.

Confidentiality & data protection

- Transcribers **MUST** treat all recordings, metadata, and transcripts as confidential and process them only within approved, secure environments (e.g. access control, encryption, no third-party disclosure without authorisation).
- They **MUST** follow project-internal and legal requirements (e.g. NDAs, retention periods, deletion policies); they **SHOULD** document access and transfers (audit trail).

Independence & fairness

- Transcribers **MUST** maintain content neutrality (no content-altering interventions beyond what the chosen style requires).
- They **SHOULD** disclose conflicts of interest and escalate deviations/problems early (poor audio quality, unclear speakers, etc.).

Working methods & quality assurance

- Transcribers **MUST** use appropriate tools (high-quality headphones, stable playback software, timecode support).
- They **SHOULD** apply a four-eyes principle or self-review (second pass), especially for **FV** or scientifically relevant projects.

- They **MAY** keep a brief decision log (e.g. chosen alias tags, special spellings, agreed number formats).

Safety & versioning

- Transcribers **MUST** maintain versioned files (e.g. v1.0, v1.1) and briefly document changes (changelog), where the tools in use support versioned backups.
- They **MAY** use validation checks (spellcheck, format linting, tag scanners) as long as these do not conflict with data protection policies.

Non-compliance / escalation.

In cases of systematic deviation (e.g. tag inconsistency, violation of the per-minute timestamp rule), the transcript **MUST** be sent back for revision; if needed, a coaching/feedback loop follows.

Short checklist for transcribers

- Has the correct style (**CR/CV/FV**) been chosen and applied consistently?
- Are tags in square brackets, in lower case, and used consistently? Are time ranges used for events?
- Is the one-per-minute timestamp rule respected? Are duration thresholds observed?
- Have uncertainties been marked instead of guessed?
- Has confidentiality been maintained, including secure storage/transfer?

1.2 Responsibility of clients (commissioning parties): briefing, quality, format/encoding preferences

Purpose. This chapter describes which preparatory steps and decisions clients should take so that transcripts can be produced efficiently, consistently, and in a way that is usable for research.

Pre-briefing (MUST/SHOULD/MAY)

Scope & style

- Clients **MUST** state the goal and intended use (e.g. research, UX, publication) and define the desired style (**CR/CV/FV**), including any deviations (e.g. additional markings).

Audio quality

- Clients **SHOULD** provide the cleanest and most level audio possible (low compression/artefacts, minimised crosstalk); for multichannel material, a brief channel description should be included where applicable.
- They **SHOULD** point out known problem areas (e.g. strong background noise, dialects, segments with overlap).

Speaker information

- Clients **SHOULD** provide a speaker list with clear IDs, roles/functions and, if known, gender/pronouns; they **MAY** additionally send seating plans, meeting agendas or timecodes of key events (this supports diarisation).

Terminology & dictionaries

- Clients **MUST**, in specialised domains, provide relevant word lists: terminology, proper names, product/brand names, acronyms, style conventions, and, where helpful, pronunciation guidance.
- They **SHOULD** clarify language/region settings (e.g. DE vs. AT spelling; EN-US vs. EN-GB).

Formatting & encoding

- Clients **MUST** specify the desired output formats (e.g. DOCX/TXT/CSV/JSON; optionally TEI P5/ISO 24624-compatible exports) and character encoding (recommended: UTF-8).

- They **SHOULD** define the timecode convention (start offset, HH:MM:SS or HH:MM:SS.mmm; media timecode vs. zero-based) and whether time-range notation for events is desired (e.g. “[silence 00:03:12–00:03:18]”).
- They **SHOULD** communicate preferences for numbers, date/time formats, quotation marks, hyphenation and compounds (see Section 3 for language-specific defaults).

Tagging policy

- Clients **MAY** decide whether canonical English tag labels or language-local aliases are used; within a transcript, this choice remains consistent even in multilingual material.
- They **MAY** define additional project-specific tags (definition + example + usage criteria).

Thresholds & QA

- Clients **SHOULD** confirm the per-minute timestamp rule and duration thresholds, or override them for the project (including justification and QA plan).
- They **SHOULD** define expectations for review/acceptance (e.g. blind review, sample-based inter-annotator agreement).

Legal aspects & data protection

- Clients **MUST** ensure that consent/legal bases for processing are in place (especially for personal data).
- They **SHOULD** define transfer channels and storage locations (e.g. SFTP, encrypted platforms) and communicate retention and deletion periods where these differ from the transcription provider’s standard offering.

Delivery & exchange formats (recommendations)

Input: audio/video (ideally high-quality master files or high-bitrate exports), metadata (speaker list, agenda), terminology CSV.

Output: transcript in the selected style + metadata sheet (project, style, version, deviations), optionally structured formats (TEI/ISO) for research.

Checklist

Purpose/use case: ...

Desired style: **CR / CV / FV** (deviations: ...)

Audio sources (format, channels, specifics): ...

Speaker information (IDs/roles): ...

Terminology list(s) attached? Yes/No; source/responsible: ...

Tag variant: EN-canonical / language-local (alias: ...)

Timecode convention: start offset ...; HH:MM:SS(.mmm) ...; time-range tags Yes/No

Output format(s) & encoding: ... (UTF-8 recommended)

QA/acceptance: (review mode, IAA target, sample size) ...

Data protection/transfer (channel, retention periods): ...

Note on special requirements. Deviations from the defaults (e.g. denser timestamping, additional tags, specific typography) increase effort and should be clarified in writing before the project starts (costs, turnaround time, QA adjustments).

2 Taxonomy of the Amberscript styles

2.1 Short definitions (normative + purpose-bound)

Clean Read (CR)

Clean Read (CR) aims at maximum readability in a written register while strictly preserving semantic content. Spoken language is transformed so that the meaning remains unchanged, but the form becomes clearer, more coherent, and easy to read as prose. This makes **CR** suitable for contexts where ease of understanding is central, without shifting the interpretation.

On the lexical level, colloquial forms and redundant discourse markers are normalised; disfluencies and hesitation markers (e.g. “uh”, “um”, “you know”) are omitted. Fillers are only retained if they carry a genuine nuance of meaning; any shift in meaning is excluded. The result is a precise, unambiguous text with no loss of content.

Syntax and punctuation follow a lean, consistent scheme. Ellipses (“...”) appear only in cases of genuine sentence abandonment and are not used to mark pauses. Em dashes or dash-style insertions do not replace commas and are used only where they are syntactically and semantically necessary. The goal is a clear sentence architecture that prioritises reading flow over typographic effects.

Paralinguistic events and tags are reduced to what is relevant and are written in lower case (e.g. [laughs], [sighs], [applause]). Backchannels are normalised as answers—in English “Yes/No”, in German “Ja/Nein”, in NL/FR accordingly—and thus integrated into the propositional structure instead of remaining mere listener signals. Emphatic highlighting is omitted; meaning is conveyed through word choice and sentence structure, not through typographic means.

Purpose: **Clean Read** is designed for maximum readability in a written register while preserving semantic content.

Lexicon: Colloquial forms and redundant discourse markers are normalised; disfluencies and hesitation markers are omitted; fillers/filler words are retained only if they convey a nuance of meaning. Shifts in meaning are excluded.

Syntax/punctuation: Punctuation is lean and consistent; ellipses (“...”) appear only with genuine sentence abandonment; dash insertions do not replace commas.

Paralinguistics/tags: Only relevant non-verbal events are captured; backchannels are normalised as answers (EN: Yes/No, DE: Ja/Nein, NL/FR accordingly).

Emphasis: Omitted in favour of increased readability.

Norm status: CR **MUST** preserve meaning, use lower-case tags, and comply with the per-minute timestamp rule; CR **SHOULD** avoid typographic emphasis and restrict non-verbal markings to what is relevant; CR **MAY** apply cautious stylistic smoothing (e.g. gentle adjustments in word order) as long as no shift in meaning occurs.

Clean Verbatim (CV)

Clean Verbatim (CV) combines literalness with careful smoothing in order to remain both readable and suitable for analysis. The goal is a text that largely preserves the original wording while being minimally smoothed where this demonstrably improves comprehension—without corrections of content or shifts in meaning.

On the lexical level, minor corrections in grammar and orthography are permitted (e.g. simple agreement or typing errors). Filler words are largely retained, as they reflect discourse structure and speaker stance; purely hesitant sounds such as “äh/uh/erm” are omitted because they carry no semantic added value. The guiding principle is: retain what is useful for interpretation; remove what merely signals acoustic hesitation.

Sentence structure and punctuation follow the lean CR principle. Punctuation is applied consistently and sparingly; ellipses (“...”) appear only in cases of genuine sentence abandonment and are not used to mark pauses. This keeps the syntactic surface calm without being unfaithful to the spoken delivery.

Paralinguistics and tags are written in lower case and used only for relevant non-verbal events, e.g. [laughs], [sighs], [applause]. Backchannels are retained as answers. This keeps interactional signals present in the text without over-interpreting them.

Emphasis follows the CR rules: typographic highlighting is omitted. Meaningful content is conveyed through word choice and syntax, not through graphic means.

Purpose: **Clean Verbatim** combines literalness with moderate smoothing to ensure good readability and analytical usability.

Lexicon: Minor corrections in grammar and orthography are permitted; filler words are largely retained; pure hesitation sounds (e.g. “äh/uh/erm”) are omitted.

Syntax/punctuation: Sentence structure and punctuation follow the lean CR principle; ellipses mark only genuine abandonments.

Paralinguistics/tags: Relevant non-verbal events are marked (e.g. “[laughs]”); backchannels are retained as answers and notated in a language-specific way.

Emphasis: As in CR.

Norm status: CV **MUST** preserve literal wording without correcting meaning, comply with the per-minute timestamp rule, and write tags in lower case; CV **SHOULD** apply minimal corrections where these measurably improve intelligibility without shifting content; CV **MAY** retain discourse markers insofar as they are analytically useful.

Full Verbatim (FV)

Full Verbatim (FV) aims at maximum level of detail for research and fine-grained analysis. It represents the spoken language as fully as possible – including its disorder, repetitions, and speech phenomena – without interpretive smoothing. **FV** is therefore the format of choice when interactional dynamics, repair processes, speaker stance, prosodic cues or interaction signals need to remain empirically visible and analysable.

On the lexical level, no corrections are made: neither grammatical nor orthographic interventions (in the sense of preserving the lexical form) are permitted. Filler words and hesitation sounds are systematically captured; self-corrections, restarts and immediate repetitions likewise remain in place. The documentary principle is: everything audible that may have analytical value is preserved. Where there are variants (e.g. “mhm” vs. “mm-hmm”), the language-specific conventions apply.

Syntax and punctuation are not used for smoothing but for precise marking of speech events. Word cut-offs are marked with a hyphen (“-”), sentence abandonments exclusively with an ellipsis (“...”). Pause length, lengthening and other prosodic phenomena are notated consistently. The aim is a reproducible, formally unambiguous surface that preserves the granularity of the data.

Paralinguistics and tags are captured comprehensively: laughter, sighs, audible and meaning-bearing in- and exhalations, pauses, relevant background noises, technical disturbances and co-occurring events (e.g. [phone rings], [door opens]). Backchannels appear in their original, language-specific form, as they themselves are objects of investigation as interactional signals. Event tags must be written in lower case, with explicit start/end markers whenever the duration is ≥ 3 s; shorter, punctual events are notated as instant tags, as described in Chapter 3. Overlaps and entries by other speakers are documented where they affect intelligibility or the interactional structure.

Emphasis is marked typographically only when there is a clear, audible stress. The default is ALL CAPS for the affected word or morpheme; as a rule of thumb, we recommend two to three markings per minute and per speaker in order not to overload the reading flow while preserving the signalling function. Where analytically needed, local patterns of stress may additionally be documented (e.g. a standardised “[emph]”); for reasons of consistency, however, the primary recommendation is to use ALL CAPS.

Purpose: **Full Verbatim** addresses maximum detail for research and fine-grained analysis.
Lexicon: No corrections are made; filler words and hesitation sounds (e.g. “äh/uh/erm”) are recorded; repetitions remain intact.

Syntax/punctuation: Word cut-offs are marked with a hyphen (“-”), sentence abandonments with an ellipsis (“...”).

Paralinguistics/tags: Non-verbal phenomena (laughter, sighs, pauses, noises) are captured comprehensively; backchannels appear in their original, language-specific form.

Emphasis: ALL CAPS is used only where clear audible emphasis is present; as a guideline, two to three instances per minute and speaker are recommended to balance readability and signalling function. Additional local emphasis markers (e.g. “[emph]”) may be used where analytically necessary, but the primary recommendation is a unified ALL CAPS convention.

Norm status: FV **MUST** ensure the completeness of audible features, comply with the per-

minute timestamp rule, and apply a duration threshold of ≥ 3 s for start/end markers of event tags; FV **SHOULD** adhere strictly and consistently to symbol conventions and document overlaps where they affect intelligibility; FV **MAY** – in line with these guidelines – use fine-grained timing annotations (sub-second) where supported by the tooling and clearly required for analytical purposes.

Core norms (cross-style)

ags are consistently written in lower case and enclosed in square brackets. The default is the canonical English form ([inaudible], [silence], [crosstalk], [foreign language]); this facilitates downstream processing in international contexts. Language-specific aliases (e.g. [überlappung], [fremdsprache]) are permitted as long as a single variant is used consistently within a transcript. The choice of variant must be fixed at the start of the project and documented in the metadata.

The per-minute timestamp rule limits time-marking to at most one timestamp per minute and speaker turn. This substantially increases readability and does not impair orientation, because time spans for longer events are marked precisely via the event tags themselves. A “turn” is a continuous stretch of speech by one speaker; when the speaker changes, a new turn begins.

For start/end timestamps on event tags, duration thresholds apply: in **CR/CV** from ≥ 5 s, in **FV** from ≥ 3 s. Shorter occurrences are captured as point events without an end time. We recommend time-range notation within the tags themselves, e.g. [silence 00:03:12–00:03:18] (format HH:MM:SS; milliseconds optional if analytically required, and then used consistently throughout the transcript). This practice keeps the running text lean while still providing analysable duration information.

Mapping note. For central events there are fixed correspondences to established standards:
“[laughs]” → TEI <vocal desc="laughter"> / ISO event=laughter;
“[silence]” → TEI <pause dur="..."> / ISO pause;
“[crosstalk]” or “[überlappung]” → TEI <overlap> / ISO overlap.

Word and sentence truncations follow the Jefferson/GAT2 equivalents (specified in a language-specific way in Chapter 3). This keeps our symbol practices across the three styles (**CR/CV/FV**) interoperable with external annotation traditions.

What is “mapping” and why is it interesting?

“Mapping” refers to the systematic alignment of Amberscript-internal tags and symbols with elements/attributes of formal standards (e.g. TEI P5, ISO 24624) and with conversation-analytic notation (Jefferson, GAT2). Good mapping creates interoperability (seamless import/export workflows to ELAN, EXMARaLDA, Praat, TEI-XML), comparability (cross-corpus querying for, e.g., laughter, pauses, overlaps), reproducibility (a clear, tool-independent meaning for each symbol), and citability (terminology that fits into scholarly discourse). In practical terms, this means that a transcript produced under the Amberscript Guidelines can be converted into standardised formats without loss of information, combined with other datasets, and further processed by research teams and NLP pipelines—today and in the near future.

Tags: Tags are written in lower case and enclosed in square brackets; the canonical English forms ([inaudible], [silence], [crosstalk], [foreign language]) are permitted. Language-specific aliases (e.g. [überlappung], [fremdsprache]) are recommended; within a single transcript, one variant must be used consistently.

Per-minute timestamp rule: Each speaker turn may contain at most one timestamp per minute. This greatly enhances readability without having any meaningful negative impact on

temporal orientation.

Duration thresholds: For start/end timestamps of event tags, the thresholds are CR/CV \geq 5 s, FV \geq 3 s. Time-range notation: the recommended form is “[silence 00:03:12–00:03:18]” (HH:MM:SS, milliseconds optional if clearly required for analysis).

Mapping note: The main correspondences are: “[laughs]” → TEI <vocal desc="laughter"> / ISO event=laughter; “[silence]” → TEI <pause dur="..."> / ISO pause; “[crosstalk]” or “[überlappung]” → TEI <overlap> / ISO overlap. Word and sentence truncations follow the Jefferson/GAT2 equivalents (specified in a language-specific way in Chapter 3).

2.2 Operations by style (cross-style overview with clarifications)

Lexicon

In the lexical domain, the three styles interact with different degrees of intervention. **Clean Read (CR)** should normalise colloquial forms and redundant discourse markers and remove purely phonetic fillers, without shifting meaning. The decisive criterion is whether an expression contributes semantically and functionally to the propositional content: if it does not, it is omitted; if it does, it is, where reasonable and result-oriented, rendered in neutral written language. **Clean Verbatim (CV)** must preserve the wording and should make minor orthographic and grammatical corrections where these increase intelligibility without changing the content; filler words are generally retained, pure hesitation sounds are omitted. **Full Verbatim (FV)** must remain fully close to the data: corrections are excluded; filler words, hesitation sounds, repetitions and self-repairs are systematically captured and documented in such a way that later qualitative or quantitative analysis remains possible.

Conceptually, a precise distinction is made between disfluency/hesitation sound as purely phonetic delay (e.g. äh/uh/erm) without lexical meaning and filler word/discourse marker as a lexical element with a pragmatic-discursive function (e.g. kind of, like). While **CR** always removes disfluencies and deletes or smooths discourse markers only where their removal does not cause loss of meaning, **CV** and **FV** generally retain discourse markers (FV always, CV with moderate smoothing where necessary).

Syntax and punctuation

For **CR** and **CV**, a reduced punctuation inventory is binding: ellipses (“...”) appear only in cases of genuine sentence abandonment; dash insertions are not used as a substitute for commas. Syntactic nesting is avoided in order to increase readability and transparency. **FV** must mark word break-offs with a hyphen (“-”) and sentence abandonments with an ellipsis (“...”); any language-specific alternatives (e.g. en dash) are defined in Chapter 3. The principle is consistency over variety: within a given transcript, a single, consistent symbol inventory is maintained so that self-repairs and restarts remain recognisable as such.

Paralinguistics and tags

The treatment of paralinguistic events follows a relevance hierarchy. **CR** should mark only those non-verbal events that make a content contribution or have a clear communicative function (e.g. ironic laughter, a long meaning-bearing pause, thematically embedded sounds). Backchannels are normalised to answers (EN: Yes/No, DE: Ja/Nein, NL/FR analogously) and otherwise omitted. **CV** must mark relevant non-verbal events (e.g. “[laughs]”, “[sighs]”) and should retain backchannels where they function as answers, in a language-specific notation. **FV** must capture non-verbal phenomena and reproduce backchannels in their original form; where there is ambiguity, brief bracketed disambiguation is permitted (e.g. EN: Mhm [affirmative]) if this stabilises the interpretation.

Overlap (speaker change)

Overlaps are marked when they reduce intelligibility or when determining turn boundaries is analytically relevant. The tag choice follows the canonical **[crosstalk]**; a time range is given once the respective threshold is reached (CR/CV ≥ 5 s, FV ≥ 3 s). If utterances remain fully intelligible despite overlap and no interactional analysis is intended, the marking should be omitted.

Emphasis

Emphatic highlighting is used sparingly. ALL CAPS is used only in **FV** and only where there is clearly audible emphasis; as a guideline, no more than two to three instances per minute and per speaker are recommended, in order to preserve both reading flow and signalling function. In **FV**, the word-level marker “[emph]” can be used as an alternative where capitalisation would impair readability or where it is to be combined with prosodic annotation.

Timestamping

The per-minute timestamp rule is mandatory: per speaker turn, at most one timestamp per minute. Long events additionally receive start and end markers according to the duration thresholds ($CR/CV \geq 5$ s, $FV \geq 3$ s). Timestamps are placed at the beginning of the turn or immediately before the relevant event/tag. Each transcript chooses one tag variant (canonical EN forms or localised aliases) and uses it consistently throughout. The recommended time-range notation is “[silence 00:03:12–00:03:18]” in the format HH:MM:SS (optionally with milliseconds).

Backchannels (precise rules)

In **CR**, backchannels are normalised to Yes/No (EN) only when they function as answers; otherwise they are omitted. **CV** retains backchannels in language-specific notation when they function as answers. **FV** documents backchannels in their original form, including phonetic variants; where there is ambiguity, brief bracketed additions are useful.

Mini-example (contrastive, DE)

A spoken utterance is reproduced in **FV** in full, including hesitation sounds and sentence abandonments, smoothed in **CV**, and in **CR** transferred into the normalised written form. This keeps the methodological relationship between readability, literalness and level of detail transparent and verifiable.

Consistency note

Equivalent forms such as **[foreign language]/[fremdsprache]** or **[crosstalk]/[überlappung]** are not mixed. The canonical base is English; local aliases are recommended. The decision is taken once per transcript or project and then applied consistently.

3 Language-specific rules

This section specifies language-specific norms for English (EN) within the Amberscript styles **CR/CV/FV**. The guiding principle is coherence over variation: where variants exist (US/UK spelling; 12/24-hour time; character variants), a transcript chooses one option and applies it consistently.

Numbers, measurements & units (MUST/SHOULD)

Number spelling. Digits 0–9 are written out (zero to nine); from 10 upwards, numerals are used (10, 42, 1,003,298). **SHOULD** exceptions: measurements with units, tables/columns, technical identifiers, IDs and date/time values may consistently be written as numerals (e.g. 3 km, 5 min, Table 7).

Thousands and decimals. Use a comma for thousands (1,003,298) and a decimal point for fractions (0.42). For four-digit numbers without risk of ambiguity, the thousands separator is optional (1000 vs. 1,000); a transcript **SHOULD** decide once per project and remain consistent.

Percentages. Numeral + percent sign without a space (42%). In running text, percent may be written out where this improves readability (“twenty percent”); maintain consistency within a transcript.

Currencies. The currency symbol precedes the number without a space: \$25, £9.50, €1.30. **SHOULD**: In multi-currency contexts, allow ISO codes (USD 25, US\$25) and use them consistently. Negative amounts are written with a sign: −\$12.50.

Units. Use a non-breaking space between number and unit (10 km, 5 min). Exception: % (no space). Temperature: SI-conform 25 °C; the widely used alternative 25°C is acceptable but must be used consistently. Plurals: the unit itself does not take a plural marker (5 kg, not 5 kgs).

Time spans & decades. Decades are written as 1980s or the '80s (with an apostrophe before the shortened number). Avoid: 80's (apostrophe plural). Use an en dash for ranges: 1998–2002, 3–5%, 5–7 km.

Date & time (SHOULD)

Time formats. Prefer the 12-hour format with a.m./p.m. (lower case, with periods): 3:05 p.m. Alternative: 24-hour format 15:05. A transcript chooses one format. Time zones: 3:05 p.m. CET / 15:05 CET. With seconds/milliseconds where analytically needed: 03:05:17.250 p.m. / 15:05:17.250.

Date formats. US style: March 5, 2025; international: 5 March 2025. Weekdays can be added as needed. Avoid ordinals in formal contexts. For metadata, ISO 8601 (2025-03-05) is recommended for machine processing.

Spelling & typography (SHOULD)

Variant (US/UK). A transcript chooses US (e.g. color, analyze) or UK (colour, analyse) spelling and stays consistent, including -ize/-ise endings and program/programme differences.

Loanwords. Retain the original spelling where a term is not fully anglicised (café, résumé; acceptable: email). Proper names and technical terms are reproduced in their original form.

Quotation marks. Use typographic curly quotes: “double” / ‘single’. Periods and commas follow the chosen convention: usually inside the quotation marks in American usage, often outside in British usage—choose one variant and apply it consistently. Use the typographic apostrophe ’ (not the straight ’).

Hyphens/compounds. Use a hyphen in prenominal compounds (well-known researcher, decision-making process); do not hyphenate -ly adverb + adjective (highly qualified staff). Closed vs. open compounds follow dominant field usage (dataset vs. data set → decide project-wide). Dashes: use an en dash (–) for ranges, an em dash (—) **not** as a comma replacement (see Section 2.2).

Backchannels & paralinguistics (MUST/SHOULD)

CR. Normalise affirmative/negative backchannels → *Yes/No* (only when they function as answers); otherwise omit them.

CV/FV. Retain backchannels (partially) in their original form: *Mm-hmm* (= affirmative), *Mm-mm* (= negative); common alternatives *uh-huh/uh-uh* are permitted, but must be used consistently across the project. Optional disambiguation via *[affirmative]/[negative]* should be used sparingly and only where there is genuine ambiguity.

Hesitation sounds. *uh/um/er*: remove in **CV**, record in **FV** (choose one spelling and keep it consistently).

Non-verbal phenomena. **CV**: mark relevant events (*[laughs]*, *[sighs]*); **FV**: capture them comprehensively (including pauses, noises, prosody). Canon of tags: *[silence]*, *[inaudible]*, *[crosstalk]*, *[music]*, *[noise]*, *[foreign language]*.

Overlaps (SHOULD/MUST)

Mark overlaps only when intelligibility is reduced or turn boundaries are analytically relevant (**SHOULD**). In such cases, **[crosstalk]** **MUST** be used and, once the duration threshold is reached, a time range must be given (CR/CV ≥ 5 s, FV ≥ 3 s). Overlaps that remain fully intelligible and are analytically irrelevant should not be marked.

Mini examples (EN)

Source. “Uh, I kinda didn’t sign the agreement, actually.”

FV. “Uh, I kinda didn’t sign the agreement, actually.”

CV. “I kinda didn’t sign the agreement, actually.”

CR. “I didn’t sign the agreement.”

Backchannel.

Source. A: “Can you send it today?” — B: “Mm-hmm.”

CV/FV. “Mm-hmm.” (optional: [*affirmative*])

CR. “Yes.”

Edge cases & checkpoints (QC)

Mixed variants (US/UK, 12h/24h): do not mix; record the chosen variant in the header/metadata.

Percent + sentence combinations: use *between 5–7%* (en dash) rather than *between 5 to 7%*; ensure consistency for standalone percentage values.

Large numbers: use a comma as thousands separator; in technical IDs, omit separation where it would interfere with identification.

Currency in running text: on first mention, optionally include ISO code (*US\$25*); afterwards use the short form (*\$25*)—consistently.

Time with zone: *3:05 p.m. CET* or *15:05 CET*; consider UTC offsets for international datasets (*15:05 UTC+1*).

Quote punctuation: choose US or UK convention once and apply it consistently; ensure typographic quotation marks are used.

Spelling of hesitation sounds: decide project-wide on *uh/um* or *er* (accent/dialect dependent) and use consistently in **FV**.

Backchannel forms: choose either *Mm-hmm/Mm-mm* or *uh-huh/uh-uh*; do not mix.

Summary. English (EN) primarily requires consistency in number formatting, date/time formats, spelling variants and paralinguistic conventions. Where alternatives are permitted, one option is chosen and applied consistently; **CR/CV/FV** differ mainly in their degree of intervention, not in the choice of spelling variant.

4 Tagging and timestamps

4.1 Basic form

The formal markup follows a strictly normative core that ensures interoperability with tool chains, verifiability in quality assurance, and the citability of transcripts. Tags are written consistently in lower case, enclosed in square brackets, and kept in an ASCII-compatible form (e.g. [inaudible], [silence], [crosstalk], [foreign language]). This canonical set avoids encoding artefacts and facilitates machine processing. Local aliases are permitted (e.g. [überlappung], [fremdsprache]) but must not be mixed with the canonical EN terms within a given transcript or project. In projects with tooling-related constraints, one of the two variants (EN canon or local alias) is chosen once and then applied consistently; where possible, an ASCII-like transcription is recommended even for aliases (e.g. [ueberlappung] instead of [überlappung]) in order to maximise system compatibility.

The per-minute timestamp rule is mandatory: per speaker turn, at most one timestamp is set per full minute. Events or states of substantial duration are annotated as time spans; the duration thresholds are ≥ 5 s in **CR/CV** and ≥ 3 s in **FV**. In such cases, time-range notation is used, specifying start and end in HH:MM:SS (optionally with milliseconds), for example: [silence 00:03:12–00:03:18]. For the placement of time markers, the following applies: timestamps are placed at the beginning of a turn or immediately before the relevant event/tag, so that the temporal reference remains unambiguous without fragmenting the reading flow unnecessarily.

4.2 Time formats & precision

Time values in transcripts are to be understood as media-relative: the zero point corresponds to the start of the recording (00:00:00); time zones or calendar schemes are not involved. To ensure readability, tool compatibility and reproducibility, each project should define one timecode format and apply it consistently. Recommended formats are **HH:MM:SS** (hours, minutes, seconds, each two digits, zero-padded) or – for finer resolution – **HH:MM:SS.m** with a decimal point as the millisecond separator (one digit, zero-padded). The seconds component must not exceed 60; roll-over (e.g. 00:59:60 → 01:00:00) is handled by carrying over into the next higher unit.

The choice between second and millisecond resolution follows the purpose-binding principle of the styles: in **CR** and **CV**, second-level resolution is usually sufficient; **FV** and research-oriented analyses should provide milliseconds where interactional dynamics (overlaps, repairs, pause lengths) require this. If milliseconds are used, values should be rounded to 0.1 s (100 ms). This threshold balances measurement accuracy and cognitive processing load, minimises visual noise, and roughly corresponds to the just noticeable difference for temporal events in conversation. A stricter resolution (e.g. 10 ms) may be used where the tooling reliably supports this precision and the analytical gain justifies the annotation effort; over-precise pseudo-accuracy should be avoided. Rounding rules are to be applied symmetrically in the usual arithmetic way ($\geq 5 \rightarrow$ round up), including carry-over into seconds (00:01:09.950 → 00:01:10.000).

Time values for states (e.g. [silence], [music]) can be notated as ranges with start–end. For range marking, the en dash (–) is typographically preferred (e.g. [silence 00:03:12–00:03:18]); where ASCII constraints apply, the hyphen (-) may be used as a fallback but must then be used consistently throughout the transcript. Semantically, a half-open interval convention applies: the start time belongs to the event, the end time marks the first moment after the event. This convention prevents overlaps between adjacent ranges and facilitates machine aggregation. For point-like events (e.g. [laughs]), a single time point (00:05:11) can suffice where no duration analysis is intended; otherwise, a short span should be used (00:05:11.0–00:05:11.6). Note that the goal is not to mark *how* something is said (e.g. laughing, crying); duration is therefore negligible unless it is analytically necessary.

The placement of time markers follows the principle outlined in **4.1**: timestamps are placed at the beginning of the turn or immediately before the relevant event/tag. For longer states, the start is placed directly before the tag (e.g. ... [silence 00:01:03–00:01:09]), with the end encoded inside the brackets. Where per-minute timestamps are used (≤ 1 per minute and speaker turn), additional nearby point markers that are purely redundant should be avoided; the minute-level ticks serve low-frequency orientation, while range specifications provide content-level precision.

For overlaps, a timeline-based approach is recommended. If the duration exceeds the style-specific threshold (CR/CV ≥ 5 s; FV ≥ 3 s) or intelligibility is impaired, a range with [crosstalk Start–End] should be set.

Drift and jitter must be addressed as potential error sources. If audio/video tracks are out of sync or transcoding has led to slight length deviations, a global offset (e.g. +120 ms) should be recorded in the metadata; wherever possible, the source material should be remuxed or

resampled before annotation. For segment-wise work, local calibration (e.g. using claps/plosives) can be useful, provided that the benefit outweighs the added complexity. In all cases, the principle is: coherence over granularity—a slightly coarser but consistently applied time norm yields more robust comparability than a highly fine-grained but inconsistently applied one.

Finally, the project should establish a validation heuristic:

- (a) syntactic validation of the format (regex for HH:MM:SS(.m));
- (b) monotonicity of time series (start < end, no backwards jumps);
- (c) boundary checks against media length (end ≤ total duration);
- (d) tolerance window for round-trips into external formats (±100 ms on export/import).

One example configuration would be: time format **HH:MM:SS.mmm**; rounding to **0.1 s**; interval convention **[start, end)**; range dash **en dash**; ASCII fallback “-” in environments without Unicode; milliseconds only in **FV**. These parameters should be stated explicitly in the document’s front matter/methods section and applied throughout.

4.3 Speaker labelling & overlaps

Speaker labelling is the primary reference frame for any transcript structure. Speaker labels must be consistent and unambiguous and must remain unchanged throughout the entire transcript. Acceptable forms include role-based labels tied to speech acts (Interviewer, Moderator), pseudonymised codes (SPK_01, SPK_02), or project-specific identifiers (Participant A). The core **MUST** requirement is uniqueness (each voice is assigned to exactly one label); a **SHOULD** requirement is stability across files/sessions within the same project. Where personal data should be avoided, an ASCII-compatible pseudonymisation backed by metadata is recommended; name variants must not be used in parallel. Unclear assignments may be marked temporarily as SPK_UNK (or SPK_UNK1, UNK_F, UNK_M); once clarified, they must be normalised retroactively and consistently. Noise sources and collectives receive their own labels (AUD for audience, SYS for system voice) in order to semantically anchor paralinguistic tags (e.g. AUD: [laughs]).

Turn definition and placement

A turn begins with the speaker label followed by the spoken content. Timestamps are placed at the beginning of the turn or immediately before the relevant event/tag (see 4.1). The per-minute timestamp rule (≤ 1 timestamp per minute and speaker turn) remains binding; longer events receive start–end ranges according to the duration thresholds (CR/CV ≥ 5 s, FV ≥ 3 s) in the recommended time-range notation ([tag HH:MM:SS–HH:MM:SS]).

Overlaps

Overlaps are marked only when they reduce intelligibility or when turn boundaries or interactional dynamics are analytically relevant. In such cases, a range with [crosstalk Start–End] (alias, for example, [überlappung]) should be used; the chosen tag variant is not mixed within a transcript. If utterances remain fully intelligible despite the overlap and no analytical added value results, the overlap should not be marked.

Prioritisation for simultaneous events

When several events occur at the same time (e.g. laughter during an overlap), the marking relevant for intelligibility has priority. In practice, the most important event is tagged first (here: [crosstalk ...]). A secondary event can be added within the same range without opening a second range, in order to avoid over-tagging and visual fragmentation. Two accepted strategies are:

- (a) a composite list within a single range ([crosstalk; laughs 00:03:12–00:03:18]), or
- (b) serial inline tagging one after another ([crosstalk 00:03:12–00:03:18] [laughs]), applied consistently throughout the transcript.

In **FV** contexts where prosodic detail is under analysis, the second variant can be advantageous, as point-like events (e.g. [laughs], [sighs]) can be recorded without their own duration ranges.

Edge cases

Short, purely phonetic overlap onsets with no loss of meaning (backchannel entries, in-breaths) are not marked. For choric responses (e.g. audience laughter), the source should be indicated with a collective label (AUD) to avoid distorting speaker statistics (AUD: [laughs 00:05:11–00:05:14]). If two speakers start at exactly the same time, the order may be determined by the first syllable perceived; if this cannot be established, the order should be

fixed project-specifically (e.g. alphabetically by label) and documented. When previously unclear voices are later identified, normalisation of the labels must be carried out retrospectively and completely.

Quality assurance

Check criteria include:

1. Uniqueness of labels (no ambiguities/variants).
2. Consistency of overlap markings (thresholds, range dash, notation variant).
3. Parsimonious use of double tags for simultaneous events.
4. Placement of timestamps in accordance with 4.1.
5. Avoidance of markings where neither intelligibility nor analytical value is affected.

This ensures a robust balance between speaker diarisation, interaction analysis, and readability.

4.4 Pauses, noises & environmental events

Classification and purpose. Pauses, noises and environmental events structure interactional dynamics, govern turn transitions, and shape intelligibility. Their annotation follows the principle of *coherence over granularity*: mark as much as necessary, as little as possible. The concrete level of intervention depends on the style: **CR** only marks where there is clear informational or communicative added value; **CV** marks relevant events; **FV** systematically captures finer phenomena where they matter for interaction or prosody analysis.

Pauses (silence).

A pause is present when no spoken sound is audible; room tone does not count as speech. Pauses are annotated as ranges and are subject to the duration thresholds (CR/CV \geq 5 s, FV \geq 3 s) and the per-minute timestamp rule. **CR** uses pauses sparingly, typically to segment longer silences or mark contentually meaningful breaks; **CV** marks pauses where they support turn organisation (e.g. hesitant onset) or expectation-building; **FV** inventories pauses systematically, including short breaks, where they are functional in the argumentation or repair structure.

MUST: do not fragment contiguous pauses into multiple segments but merge them; adjacent pause ranges must be merged if there is no intervening event. Do *not* mark as pause: masking by noise (\rightarrow [noise]) and unintelligible but present speech (\rightarrow [inaudible]).

Noises & environmental events (noise, applause, phone, door, etc.).

Non-speech, auditorily salient events are tagged when they (a) affect intelligibility, (b) are thematised in the conversation, or (c) are necessary to understand the scene (location, action, interaction mode). The tag canon is ASCII-compatible and lower case; allowed examples include [noise], [applause], [phone rings], [door closes], [typing], [coughs], [sneezes], [mic handling], [beep] (sensor tone). Projects may extend this with a controlled descriptor vocabulary (e.g. [noise traffic], [noise wind], [music background]), provided it is applied consistently throughout the transcript and complies with linting rules (ASCII, lower case). **CR** restricts itself to events relevant for understanding; **CV** additionally marks noises that are explicitly discussed; **FV** aims for broad coverage but avoids over-tagging by reasonably aggregating repetitive noise sequences (e.g. [applause 00:05:11–00:05:18] instead of multiple point marks).

Music.

Music is annotated with [music] as a range when it is audible and (a) masks speech, (b) signals scene changes, or (c) is a topic in the conversation. Optionally, its function may be added as a descriptor (e.g. [music diegetic] vs. [music nondiegetic], [music vocal] vs. [music instrumental]), provided this is defined on a project level. Singing within turns can be tagged as [music vocal] or – where the lyrics themselves are content-relevant – as speech with an additional [singing] marker; the decision is taken per project and applied consistently.

Unintelligible speech & masking (inaudible).

[inaudible] marks intended speech that cannot be understood (e.g. too quiet, masked, recording error). Where helpful, a short contextual descriptor may be added (e.g. [inaudible noise], [inaudible off-mic]) as long as tag syntax is preserved. Do *not* use [inaudible] for pauses (\rightarrow [silence]) or non-speech noises (\rightarrow [noise]). In **CR**, [inaudible] is used sparingly,

when the information loss is relevant for understanding; **CV/FV** mark it systematically, potentially with time ranges.

Simultaneous events.

When events occur at the same time (e.g. laughter during music), the event most relevant for intelligibility has priority. Secondary events can be listed within the same range ([music; laughs 00:10:02–00:10:08]) or marked serially right afterwards ([music 00:10:02–00:10:08] [laughs]). The chosen strategy is applied consistently. For overlapping speech with concurrent noise, [crosstalk] is used if intelligibility suffers; the noise can be added as a supplement ([crosstalk; noise ...]).

Position, duration & precision.

Events are annotated as ranges once they exceed the thresholds (CR/CV \geq 5 s, FV \geq 3 s). Point-like events (e.g. [coughs], [beep]) can be encoded as a single timestamp or as a short range; **FV** tends to use brief ranges (e.g. 00:05:11.0–00:05:11.6) for better reproducibility. Interval semantics follow the convention [**start, end**] (see 4.2). Rounding milliseconds to 0.1 s is recommended unless the tooling reliably works at a finer resolution.

Classification heuristics (SHOULD)

A project **SHOULD** use the following decision tree:

- (a) Is speech intended? → [inaudible] (if unintelligible), otherwise treat as speech.
- (b) Is the silence functional (break/segment boundary)? → [silence].
- (c) Is the event thematised in the conversation? → mark it (at least in **CV**).
- (d) Does it change turn organisation/prosody? → mark it in **FV**.

Do not mark events that are purely marginal (a brief chair creak without relevance) and offer no analytical added value.

Mapping notes.

In TEI/ISO, pauses are usually modelled as <pause> with @dur; non-speech events as <incident @type="music|noise|applause|...">; non-lexical vocalisations as <vocal @desc="laughter|sigh|cough">. The composite syntax chosen in running text (e.g. [noise traffic]) is mapped into @type/@subtype or @desc; overlaps receive synchronisation anchors (see Appendix A).

QC checkpoints.

- (1) Are thresholds respected?
- (2) Are adjacent pause/noise ranges merged instead of fragmented?
- (3) Is prioritisation correct for simultaneous events?
- (4) Is the chosen tag variant (canon/alias) not mixed?
- (5) Is interval format/rounding in line with 4.2?
- (6) Are events *not* tagged where there is no gain in intelligibility or analytical value?

This keeps the annotation economical, informative, and tool-compatible.

4.5 Backchannels

Definition and function.

Backchannels are short, mostly non-propositional listener signals (e.g. *mhm*, *hm*, *uh-huh*, *mm-mm*, *hum-hum*) that indicate attention, agreement, disagreement or a request to continue. They carry a communicative function but are not independent contributions to content. For language-specific spelling conventions, see Section 3.

Normative core (MUST)

CR — normalisation.

In **CR**, backchannels are normalised only when they function as answers to *Yes/No* (EN), *Ja/Nein* (DE), *Ja/Nee* (NL), *Oui/Non* (FR). Where there is no answer function or semantic added value, backchannels are omitted in CR (see Section 2.2). Normalisation serves readability and reduces ambiguity.

CV/FV — retention.

In **CV/FV**, backchannels are retained and written in a language-specific form. Ambiguities are resolved sparingly with bracketed additions: *[affirmative]/[negative]* (EN), *[bejahend]/[verneinend]* (DE), *[bevestigend]/[ontkennend]* (NL), *[affirmatif]/[négatif]* (FR).

Spelling & punctuation (SHOULD)

Orthographic variants are decided project-wide and applied consistently (e.g. *Mm-hmm/Mm-mm* or *uh-huh/uh-uh*; DE *hm/mhm*). For backchannels followed by substantive content, a comma **SHOULD** be inserted where this improves readability (“Mm-hmm, yes.” / „Hm [bejahend], ja.“). Lengthenings (*mhm-mhm-mhm*) or iterations **SHOULD** only be represented where they are functionally relevant (e.g. insistent agreement). Unnecessary variation is to be avoided.

Distinction (MUST)

Backchannels **MUST** be distinguished from:

- (a) disfluencies/hesitation sounds without function (*uh/um*; *äh/ähm*) — these are not backchannels;
- (b) lexical response items with propositional content (*yes*, *indeed*; *genau*; *certainement*) — these count as content and are not normalised.

Overlap & placement (SHOULD)

Short backchannels do not need to be marked as overlap if intelligibility is not affected (see Section 4.4). Timestamps are placed at the beginning of the backchannel turn or immediately before the backchannel where a range is tagged. Range specifications are only required for long backchannel sequences or where duration is analytically relevant (e.g. choric “mhm”).

Pauses/noise interaction (SHOULD)

Backchannels interrupt pause ranges; therefore, within a single [silence] range there **SHOULD** not be a backchannel inside the same range brackets. If a backchannel is masked (e.g. by [noise]), its semantic contribution is considered uncertain; in **CV/FV**, the backchannel may be written with or without [inaudible], depending on audibility.

QC checkpoints (MUST/SHOULD)

- (1) **MUST:** Style conformity — normalisation in **CR** vs. retention in **CV/FV**.
- (2) **MUST:** Consistent spelling variant per language (no mixing *Mm-hmm/uh-huh*).
- (3) **SHOULD:** Disambiguation only where there is genuine ambiguity.
- (4) **MUST:** No confusion between hesitation sound and backchannel.
- (5) **SHOULD:** Overlap only marked where intelligibility/analytic value is affected.
- (6) **MUST/SHOULD:** Placement and time range in line with Sections 4.1/4.2.

Summary.

Backchannels are normalised in **CR** to clear yes/no forms, retained in **CV/FV** in language-specific form, and only sparsely disambiguated where ambiguous. The rules prioritise readability, functional clarity and analytical usability, while ensuring coherence across languages and projects.

Appendix A: Transcription guidelines

General conventions

Transcripts are written in clear, legible sentences. The applicable transcription style (Clean Read, Clean Verbatim, Full Verbatim, etc.) determines how closely the wording follows the spoken language and how much smoothing is allowed.

Long, overly nested sentences are avoided. When a thought is clearly completed, a full stop is preferred over a comma. Long monologues are broken into paragraphs of roughly 10–15 lines to support readability.

The correct language variety is used according to the project (e.g. UK English EN-UK, American English EN-US, Australian English EN-AU). If no variety is specified, EN-US can be used as a default.

Context is always taken into account, both to avoid contradictions and to ensure that words are correctly identified.

If there is doubt about a word or expression, a best guess may be transcribed in parentheses followed by a question mark:

- (suspected utterance?)

Unfamiliar names, terms or expressions (e.g. cities, people, organisations, products) are researched. If no reliable spelling can be found, a phonetic best guess may be used in parentheses.

Tags in square brackets are used consistently according to the relevant style guide, for example:

- [foreign language ...]
- [silence ...]
- [unv. ...]
- [laughter] (depending on style)

Run-on sentences should be avoided. Long nested sentences are split into shorter units, following the conventions of the specific transcription style.

Transcription – recommended practices

- Write sentences that are well-structured and easy to read.
- Follow the selected transcription style (e.g. Clean Read vs. Verbatim) when deciding how strictly to follow spoken syntax and wording.
- Use punctuation consistently and in line with the rules in the section **Abbreviations, punctuation & spelling**.
- Where style allows, break up very long sentences into two or more sentences to improve readability.
- As a guideline, a sentence should not be longer than three to four lines in the editor or two to three lines in a word processor.
- Long monologues should be divided into paragraphs of around 10–15 lines.

Transcription – what to avoid

- Content should not be arbitrarily removed or altered. Entire sentences and expletives remain in the transcript unless a specific anonymisation or redaction rule applies.
- Formal contractions such as *don't*, *can't* and *it's* are left as they are spoken. Treatment of colloquial contractions like *lemme* or *gonna* depends on the chosen transcription style.
- Tags (content in square brackets) are written in lower case, for example:
 - [silence], [foreign language], [unv. ...]
- Passages that are clearly not part of the main interview (for example, a short exchange with a waiter or unrelated background conversations) are normally omitted unless explicitly required by the project.

Speaker identification

- Speakers are labelled generically as **Speaker 1**, **Speaker 2**, **Speaker 3**, etc.

- For recordings with only one speaker, that person is labelled **Speaker**.
- Each speaker change begins on a new paragraph.

Numerals

- Common currencies are written as symbols: €, \$. Other currencies are written out: *yen, won, rand, pound*. Currency names are not written in all caps.
- Numbers from **zero to nine** are written out in words:
 - *one, three, nine*
- Numbers **10 and above** are written as digits:
 - *10, 11, 12, 56*
- If a sentence contains both numbers below and above ten, digits are used for all:
 - *They are 5 and 15 years old.*
Exception: when the sentence begins with a number, it is written out:
 - *Five and 15 years ago ...*
- When a number stands at the beginning of a sentence, it is written out in full:
 - *Twenty-two people joined.*
Exception: years may begin a sentence as digits:
 - *1989 was amazing.*
- If a figure has **five or more digits**, a comma is used:
 - *50,000*
- Very large numbers may combine digits and words:
 - *45 million*

- Ordinals: *first, second, third* are written out. Higher ordinals use numerals with suffix:
 - *11th, 12th, 71st*
- Round prices are written without decimals:
 - *\$15, €26*
- Mathematical functions are written out:
 - *plus, minus, times, divided by*
- Written-out fractions are hyphenated:
 - *five-eighths*
- Mixed fractions are written in words:
 - *five and a half*
- Commas are used for large figures:
 - *1,003,298*
- A decimal point is used for decimal numbers:
 - *0.42 pounds*
- Phone numbers are written as digits:
 - *201-555-5555*
- Digits are used to indicate degrees and angles:
 - *270 degrees, an angle of 45 degrees*
- The following mathematical terms are written out as words: *infinity, faculty, percent, prime, degrees, phi, theta*.

Time and dates

- Exact times of day are written with numerals:
 - *9:30 in the morning*
- With *o'clock*, the number is written out:
 - *eleven o'clock*
- Vague times are written in words:
 - *half past four, quarter to three, midnight, noon*
- Dates are written as they are spoken:
 - *June 30, 1934* or *the 30th of June 1934*
- Decades may be written as *the 80s* or *the 1980s* (no apostrophe before the s).
- *a.m.* and *p.m.* are written in lowercase with periods.

Foreign language

- Loanwords keep their original spelling where possible, unless the word is fully anglicised (e.g. *café* from French).
- The correct plural forms of loanwords are observed:
 - *sushi* → usually unchanged
 - *ballet* → *ballets*
 - *spaghetti* → unchanged
- Some loanwords retain original plurals, especially Latin and Greek:
 - *cactus* → *cacti* or *cactuses*

- *criterion* → *criteria*
- *index* → *indices* or *indexes*
- Foreign-language sections longer than a short phrase are marked with [foreign language] and time stamps, in line with the style-specific rules.
- Short, common phrases in other languages may simply be transcribed as spoken (e.g. *Mamma mia!*).
- For longer foreign-language passages, spelling, punctuation and diacritics follow the conventions of the language in question.

Gender-inclusive language

- In Clean Read and Clean Verbatim, inclusive language is preferred where smoothing and rephrasing already occur.
- Gender-neutral pronouns are retained when a speaker refers to a person as *they/them*.
- Gender-neutral job titles are preferred wherever appropriate, for example:
 - *actor* (for all genders)
 - *firefighter* instead of *fireman*
- When rephrasing, singular *they* may be used instead of *his* or *her*:
 - *Each speaker is given their own paragraph.*

Abbreviations, punctuation and spelling

- Abbreviations are written as they are spoken.
 - *for example* is written out, not abbreviated to *e.g.*
 - *EDP* remains *EDP* and is not expanded to *electronic data processing*

- *et cetera* may be abbreviated to *etc.* (always with a period)

Only the following punctuation marks are used in transcripts; style-specific rules define how exactly they appear in Clean Read vs. Verbatim:

Full stop (.)

Every sentence ends with a full stop, even if it consists of only one word.

Question mark (?)

All direct questions end with a question mark.

Exclamation mark (!)

Used sparingly to reflect clear emphasis in the original speech.

Comma (,)

Used according to standard English punctuation to separate sentence elements, list items, independent clauses and introductory or non-essential information.

Ellipsis (...)

Depending on the style, used for pauses within a sentence, for false starts or for unfinished sentences.

Single dash (-)

Depending on the style, used for stutters, repetitions or hyphenation of words.

Double dash (--)

Depending on the style, used when a sentence is incomplete or trails off.

If a speaker is interrupted by another speaker, the interrupted sentence is considered incomplete and ends with a double dash.

Quotation marks (" ")

Used to mark direct speech, thoughts, quotations and dialogue.

Colon (:)

Used to introduce direct speech or explanations.

Parentheses ()

Reserved for suspected utterances, for example:

- (word?)

Spoken names of punctuation marks and similar meta-comments are generally not transcribed.

Exception: fixed expressions where the pronounced punctuation is clearly part of the meaning, for example:

- *No means no. Period.*

Insertions and thoughts within a sentence are separated by commas, not by hyphens or dashes.

Other punctuation marks beyond full stops, commas and question marks are used only when needed to accurately reflect structure and emphasis.

Long pauses are marked with the tag [silence] and a time stamp where this is relevant for the context or the style.

URLs are written as plain text as they appear in the browser; hyperlinks are not active in the transcript.

- Example: www.amberscript.com, not *W W W dot Amberscript dot com*.

Anonymisation

Anonymisation can be applied where required so that information cannot be traced back to specific individuals.

The following conventions apply:

- Names of persons → [person]
- Places → [location]
- Organisations and companies → [organization]
- Birthdays, email addresses and telephone numbers are anonymised in the same way.

In general, only information that can be linked to identifiable individuals is anonymised.

If several persons, organisations or places occur, they are distinguished and numbered where necessary, for example:

- [person 1], [person 2]
- [organization 1], [organization 2]

If the same person or organisation is mentioned more than once, the labelling makes it clear that it is always the same entity.

Emphasis (ALL CAPS)

- Words that are clearly and audibly emphasised in the recording may be written in ALL CAPS.
- Emphasis can be conveyed by tone, volume, pitch or deliberate pacing. Examples:
 - *I NEVER said that.*
 - *This is EXACTLY what I meant.*
- Words are not capitalised purely based on perceived importance. Emphasis should be clearly audible; interpretation alone is not sufficient.
- In case of doubt, standard casing is preferred. Consistency and accuracy are more important than frequent emphasis formatting.
- As a rough upper limit, there should not be more than two to three emphasised words per minute. This is a maximum, not a target; many recordings will contain fewer, and some none at all.

Clean Verbatim — description

In a Clean Verbatim transcription, speech is transcribed verbatim, but without slips of the tongue. Sentences are slightly smoothed by correcting minor lexical and grammatical errors.

Result

The result is a verbatim transcript that primarily conveys the content of what was said.

Readability is improved to some extent, but the transcript still reflects written spoken language.

Typical uses

Meetings, assemblies, presentations.

General rules

Elements that are included

The following are normally transcribed in Clean Verbatim:

- Filler words such as “so”, “therefore”
- Question particles such as “no?”, “right?”
- “Mm” / “hmm” as answers to direct questions, rendered as:
 - **mm-hmm** (affirmative)
 - **mm-mm** (negative)
- Context-relevant sounds, e.g.
 - [phone rings]
- Incomprehensible words or sections, e.g.
 - [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]*
- Suspected utterances, e.g.
 - (word?)
- Non-verbal expressions, e.g.
 - [laughs], [sighs]
- Pauses of about 5 seconds or more, e.g.

- [silence 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Crosstalk, if it leads to incomprehensible passages, e.g.
 - [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]*
- Foreign-language sections, e.g.
 - [foreign language 00:00:00-00:00:05]*
- Sentence interruptions, marked with ellipsis:
 - ...

*If a section is shorter than 5 seconds, only the start time is marked.

Context can justify exceptions to these rules if meaning or clarity would otherwise be distorted.

Elements that are not included

The following are normally omitted in Clean Verbatim:

- Hesitation sounds such as “uh”, “um”, “er”
- Interjections such as “oh”, “oops” unless clearly meaningful
- Word repetitions, unless used as an explicit stylistic device for emphasis
- Word interruptions and stuttering (these are smoothed or omitted)
- Speaker overlaps, unless they cause incomprehensible passages; in that case, the relevant part is tagged as [inaudible ...]
- Overlapping passages that are fully understandable on both sides are not marked as interruptions

What belongs in a Clean Verbatim transcription

- Lexical and phonetic adjustments (word slurring, swallowed endings etc.) are allowed, but sentence structure is retained.
- Accents and broken English are smoothed where possible, without changing meaning.
- Filler words and discourse markers are generally transcribed, e.g. “so”, “of course”, “like I said”, “you know”, “like”.
 - Exception: if used excessively and without contextual relevance, selected instances may be omitted, as long as the meaning of the sentence is not changed.
- Quoted speech is introduced by a colon and enclosed in quotation marks.
- Interrogative fillers such as “right?” are transcribed:
 - in the middle of a sentence with a comma before and after,
 - at the end of a sentence with a comma before and a question mark after.
- If “hm” is used as a substitute for “yes” or “no” in response to a direct question, it is rendered as:
 - **mm-hmm** for *yes*
 - **mm-mm** for *no*
 If neither applies, it is omitted.
 Exception: “Hm?” in the sense of “Excuse me?” is transcribed as “Hm?”.
- Non-verbal utterances that are relevant for the context are written in square brackets, e.g.
 - [laughs], [cries]
 The way something is said is not described, i.e. [laughs] is used rather than [laughing], [crying].
- Sounds are only transcribed if they are context-relevant, e.g. [telephone rings].

- Pauses of approximately 5 seconds or more are marked with [silence] and a time stamp.
- Incomplete or interrupted sentences (from three words upwards) are marked with
 - If a file starts in the middle of a sentence, no interruption mark is placed at the very beginning; the transcript starts with the first fully spoken word.
 - If a new thought begins after a sentence interruption, the next word is capitalised.
 - If the same thought is continued, the next word is written in lower case after the interruption or repetition.

What does not belong in a Clean Verbatim transcription

- Immediately corrected slips of the tongue.
- Hesitation sounds such as “uh”, “um”, “er”.
- Irrelevant acknowledgement tokens or backchannels, such as “ah”, “yes”, “oh” etc., unless they are important to the context.
- Word repetitions, unless used as deliberate emphasis:
 - *This is also much, much more interesting for an audience.*
- Word interruptions and stuttering (smoothed or omitted).
- Speaker overlaps, except where they cause incomprehensible passages; in that case, the overlap is tagged as [inaudible ...].
- Simultaneous speech that is fully intelligible on both sides is not treated as an interruption.

Punctuation in Clean Verbatim

Only the following punctuation marks are used:

Full stop (.)

Each sentence ends with a full stop, even if it consists of only one word.

Question mark (?)

All interrogative sentences end with a question mark.

Exclamation mark (!)

Used sparingly to reflect clear emphasis.

Comma (,)

Used to separate sentence elements, such as list items, independent clauses and introductory or non-essential information.

Quotation marks (" ")

Used to mark direct speech.

Colon (:)

Used to introduce direct speech.

Ellipsis (...)

Indicates interruptions and incomplete sentences.

Hyphen (-)

Used for hyphenated words.

Parentheses ()

Reserved for suspected utterances where the word is uncertain, e.g.

- (word?)

Transcription tags and time stamps

When using tags, context and relevance are always taken into account. Tags are written in lower case inside square brackets.

Typical mappings:

- Non-verbal affirmative sounds
→ mm-hmm

- Non-verbal negative sounds
→ mm-mm
- Incomprehensible passages (after at least three careful listening attempts, including adjusted volume and reduced speed such as 0.7)
→ [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Pauses of 5 seconds or more
→ [silence 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Crosstalk that leads to incomprehensible passages
→ [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Foreign-language sections
→ [foreign language 00:00:00-00:00:05]

Time-stamp rules:

- As a general principle, only one time stamp per tag type is used per minute.
 - The first occurrence within that minute carries the tag plus time stamp.
 - Further occurrences of the same tag within the same minute are marked with the tag only, without a time stamp, unless the duration justifies start and end times.
- Any tag with a duration of 5 seconds or longer is marked with start and end times, regardless of where it falls within the minute.
- Tags of 4 seconds or less within the same minute usually do not carry a time stamp if one has already been given for that tag type in that minute.

Example:

He said [inaudible 00:00:05-00:00:15], but then [silence] I was [foreign language]. Yes, [silence 00:00:30-00:00:36] it was not [inaudible] because we [inaudible].

Full Verbatim — description

In a Full Verbatim transcription, everything that is said is reproduced, including mistakes, slips of the tongue, stutters and false starts. Word repetitions and hesitation sounds such as "uh" and "mm-hmm" are included. Word order follows the recording. Selected non-verbal events such as laughter, crying and silence are marked.

Result

An exact transcript that not only documents what was said, but also how it was said, including hesitation, emphasis and non-verbal reactions.

Typical uses

Scientific interviews, conversations between patients and doctors, language analysis, legal documents such as hearings, and focus group interviews where emotions and interaction patterns play an important role.

General rules

Elements that are included

The following are normally transcribed in Full Verbatim:

- Filler words such as “so”, “therefore”
- Question particles such as “no?”, “right?”
- Interjections such as “oh”, “oops”
- Hesitation sounds such as “uh”, “um”, often rendered as [uh] if needed
- Non-verbal affirmative and negative responses:
 - **mm-hmm** (affirmative)
 - **mm-mm** (negative)
- Context-relevant sounds, e.g.
 - [phone rings]
- Incomprehensible words or sections, e.g.
 - [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:03]*
- Suspected utterances, e.g.
 - (word?)
- Non-verbal expressions, e.g.

- [laughs], [sighs]
- Pauses, e.g.
 - [silence 00:00:00-00:00:03]
- Crosstalk when it leads to incomprehensible passages, e.g.
 - [crosstalk 00:00:00-00:00:03]*
- Foreign-language sections, e.g.
 - [foreign language 00:00:00-00:00:03]*
- Sentence interruptions, indicated by a double dash:
 - --
- Word interruptions (stutters), indicated by a single dash:
 - -

*If a section is shorter than three seconds, only the start time is marked.

Context can justify exceptions if strict application of a rule would distort meaning.

Elements that are not omitted in Full Verbatim

In contrast to Clean Verbatim and Clean Read, the following are **kept** in Full Verbatim and are not smoothed away:

- Slips of the tongue and self-corrections
- Hesitation sounds and filled pauses (“uh”, “um”, “er”, “mm...”)
- Word repetitions and false starts
- Sentence fragments and incomplete sentences

Content is not cleaned for style; the goal is to reproduce the spoken performance as faithfully as possible.

How to create a Full Verbatim transcription

- The text is transcribed exactly as spoken.
Word order is retained, errors are not corrected, and no syntactic smoothing is

carried out.

- Phonetic adjustments (word slurring, swallowed endings etc.) may be made to bring words to standard written form, but **syntactic and lexical adjustments** (word choice and sentence structure) are not made.
- All utterances produced by all speakers are transcribed. If a speaker uses the “wrong” or unexpected word, this is transcribed as spoken.
- **Dialects:**
 - Syntax is retained.
 - Pronunciation is adapted to standard English spelling.
 - Phonetic adjustments are allowed; lexical and syntactic adjustments are not.
- Quoted speech is introduced by a colon and enclosed in quotation marks.
- All comprehension signals and filler words are transcribed, including frequent “mm-hmm”, “yeah”, “okay”, “right” etc.
- Non-verbal affirmative and negative responses are written as:
 - **mm-hmm** (affirmative)
 - **mm-mm** (negative)
If only a neutral “mm” is heard and it is unclear whether it is affirmative or negative, it may be transcribed as **mm**.
- Commas are not automatically placed before and after comprehension signals. For example:
 - *Mm-hmm. Yes, okay.*
- Short interjections by another speaker are transcribed in a separate paragraph.
- Speaker overlaps:
 - Each speaker receives their own paragraph.
 - If an overlap makes a passage unintelligible, the affected part is marked with [crosstalk ...].
 - If both parts are intelligible, no overlap tag is needed.

- **Strong emphasis:**

When a speaker clearly emphasises a word, it may be written in ALL CAPS, e.g.:

- *I NEVER said that.*

- *This is EXACTLY what I meant.*

Emphasis is used sparingly. As a rough upper limit, there should not be more than 2–3 emphasised words per minute. Decisions about emphasis are often easiest when reviewing the complete transcript with full context.

- **Pauses:**

Pauses during speech or between turns are marked with [silence].

- For pauses of 3 seconds or more, start and end times are marked:

- [silence 00:00:00-00:00:03]

- For shorter pauses, only the start time may be given:

- [silence 00:00:00]

Judgment is important: if a speaker talks slowly, it is not necessary to mark very frequent one-second pauses between almost every word.

- **Stutters and repetitions:**

- Stutters concern a single word and are marked with a **single dash** directly attached to the repeated part, e.g.:

- *I- I- I don't know.*

- Repetitions concern more than one word and are marked with a **single dash and a space**, e.g.:

- *He said- he said he'd come later.*

If stuttering is extremely frequent throughout a recording, the overall treatment can be agreed at project level; by default, stutters are transcribed as described above.

- **Sentence interruptions and incomplete sentences:**

These are included.

- If a file starts in the middle of a sentence, no interruption symbol is placed at the very beginning; the transcript begins with the first fully spoken word.

- If a new thought begins after an interruption, the next word is capitalised.

- If the same thought is continued, the next word is written in lower case after the interruption or repetition.
- **Non-verbal expressions:**
Emotional non-verbal expressions that support or clarify the statement are marked in square brackets when relevant, for example:
 - [laughs], [cries]
The way something is said is not described: use [laughs], not [laughing].
- **Interrogative fillers:**
Fillers such as “right?” and “no?” are transcribed as follows:
 - in the middle of a sentence with a comma before and after,
 - at the end of a sentence with a comma before and a question mark after.
- **Non-verbal actions or noises:**
Non-verbal actions or noises that interrupt the conversation are marked in brackets where relevant to context. Continuous background noise (e.g. traffic, office ambience, wind) is generally not tagged unless it has a specific function in the conversation.
- **Long incomprehensible passages:**
Longer incomprehensible segments can be supplemented with a brief indication of the cause where possible, and in these cases [inaudible] can be abbreviated to [inaud.], for example:
 - [inaud. music 00:00:10-00:00:25].

Punctuation in Full Verbatim

Only the following punctuation marks are used:

Full stop (.)

Each sentence ends with a full stop, even if it consists of a single word.

Question mark (?)

All interrogative sentences end with a question mark.

Exclamation mark (!)

Used to reflect clear emphasis in the original speech.

Comma (,)

Used to separate sentence elements, such as list items, independent clauses and introductory or non-essential information.

Quotation marks (" ")

Used to mark direct speech.

Colon (:)

Used to introduce direct speech.

Ellipsis (...)

Indicates incomplete or discontinued sentences, for example when a person trails off, pauses mid-sentence or produces a false start.

Single dash (-)

Used to mark stutters, repetitions and hyphenations of words.

Double dash (--)

Used when a speaker is interrupted by something external, such as another speaker or a loud noise.

Parentheses ()

Reserved for suspected utterances when a word is uncertain, for example:

- (word?)

Transcription tags and timestamps

When using tags, relevance and context are always taken into account. Tags (everything in square brackets) are written in lower case.

Typical mappings:

- Non-verbal affirmative sounds
→ mm-hmm
- Non-verbal negative sounds
→ mm-mm
- Incomprehensible passages (after: multiple listens, increased volume, and slower playback such as 0.7 speed):
→ [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:03]
- Pauses:
 - Under 3 seconds:
→ [silence 00:00:00]
 - 3 seconds or more:
→ [silence 00:00:00-00:00:03]

- Speaker overlaps that lead to incomprehensible passages:
→ [crosstalk 00:00:00-00:00:03]
- Foreign-language sections:
→ [foreign language 00:00:00-00:00:05]

Timestamp rules:

- Excluding [silence], only one timestamp per tag type is used per minute.
 - The first occurrence within a given minute is marked with tag and timestamp.
 - Further occurrences of the same tag type within the same minute are usually marked with the tag only, unless the passage is long enough to justify start and end times.
- Any tag of **3 seconds or longer** should be marked with start and end times, regardless of where in the minute it occurs.
- Tags of **2 seconds or less** within the same minute generally do not carry a timestamp if one has already been given for that tag type in that minute.

Example:

He said [inaudible 00:00:05-00:00:15], but then [silence 00:00:20] I was [foreign language]. Yes, [silence 00:00:30-00:00:36] it was not [inaudible] because we [inaudible].

Clean Read — description

In a Clean Read transcription, the text is written in standard English. Spoken grammar and syntax are corrected. The content of the recording is preserved, but no intentional stylistic “improvements” are made.

Result

A Clean Read transcript provides information about the content of what was said, using written language only. The result is a clear, easy-to-read transcript.

Typical uses

Organisation/company meetings, municipality meetings, presentations, etc.

General rules

Elements that are included

The following elements can appear in a Clean Read transcript:

- Question particles such as “no?”, “right?”
→ only if needed for meaning or nuance.
- Non-verbal affirmative and negative responses as answers to direct questions, normalised as:
 - **Yes**
 - **No**
- Incomprehensible words or sections, e.g.:
 - [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]*
- Suspected utterances, e.g.:
 - (word?)
- Foreign-language sections, e.g.:
 - [foreign language 00:00:00-00:00:05]*

Pauses of approx. 5 seconds or more and other interruptions are included only when they are relevant to the context, and then marked as:

- [silence 00:00:00-00:00:05]

*If the section is shorter than five seconds, only the start time is marked.

Elements that are not included

The following elements are normally **omitted** in Clean Read:

- Filler words such as “so”, “therefore”
- Hesitation sounds such as “uh”, “um”, “hm”
- Interjections such as “oh”, “oops” (unless clearly meaningful)
- Non-verbal expressions such as [laughs], [cries] (except when relevant to context)
- Pauses (including those of 5 seconds or more) when they are not context-relevant
- Crosstalk as such — only its effect is marked (with [inaudible ...] if something becomes unintelligible)
- Sentence interruptions and incomplete sentences as such — these are smoothed into complete sentences where possible
- Repetitions and stutters (unless used as a clear stylistic device for emphasis)

Context can justify exceptions to these rules if meaning or clarity would otherwise be changed.

How to create a Clean Read transcription

What belongs in a Clean Read transcription

- Sentences are **legible, correct and complete**.
- Grammatical, lexical and phonetic errors are corrected where this improves clarity without changing meaning.
- Sentence structure is adjusted where necessary to improve readability (e.g. splitting very long sentences, merging fragmented ones).
- Formal contractions are kept as spoken (e.g. *can't*, *won't*, *don't*).
- Colloquial contractions are written out fully (e.g. *lemme* → *let me*).
- Quoted speech is reformulated as indirect speech where possible. If there is doubt, direct speech may be used instead.
- Pauses of approx. 5 seconds or more and other interruptions are only transcribed when relevant to the context, and then marked with [silence] + time stamp.

- Speaker overlaps are given separate paragraphs for each speaker.
 - If a passage becomes unintelligible due to overlap, it is marked as [inaudible ...].
 - If both parts remain intelligible, no special marking is necessary.

What does not belong in a Clean Read transcription

- Complete sentences or expressions are not removed if they are important to the content or tone. The speaker's meaning and general style should remain recognisable.
- Sentence beginnings with conjunctions such as “and”, “but”, “or” are avoided where possible; sentences may be restructured.
- Filler words and comprehension signals are omitted.
 - Note: depending on context, some words are not purely fillers; they are only omitted if this does **not** change the meaning.
- Elliptical sentences are completed where context allows.
- Incomplete sentences with substantive meaning are expanded or converted into complete sentences where the intended meaning can be inferred.
 - If this is not possible, an ellipsis ... may be used at the end of the sentence.
- Interrupted words are either completed or left out; they are not marked as broken forms.
- Unnecessarily long sentences containing filler elements may be shortened and restructured for clarity.
- Non-verbal affirmative and negative responses are not transcribed as “mm-hmm” or “mm-mm”.
 - If they function as answers to direct questions, they are written as **Yes** or **No**.
- Word repetitions are omitted, unless they are clearly used as a stylistic device for emphasis, e.g.:
 - *That is much, much more interesting.*
- Non-verbal utterances and events ([laughs], [cries], [phone rings]) are not transcribed, unless they are relevant to the context.

- Slips of the tongue are omitted.
- Hesitation sounds such as “uh”, “um”, “hm” are not transcribed.
- Abbreviations such as *e.g.*, *i.e.*, *ok* are not used; they are written out as *for example*, *that means*, *okay*.

Punctuation in Clean Read

Only the following punctuation marks are used:

Full stop (.)

Each sentence ends with a full stop, even if it consists of a single word.

Question mark (?)

All interrogative sentences end with a question mark.

Exclamation mark (!)

Used sparingly to convey strong emphasis.

Comma (,)

Used to separate sentence elements such as list items, independent clauses and introductory or non-essential information, according to standard English punctuation rules.

Quotation marks (" ")

Used to mark direct speech (if indirect speech is not chosen).

Colon (:)

Used to introduce direct speech or explanatory elements.

Ellipsis (...)

Used only when sentence interruptions or discontinued sentences cannot be avoided, e.g. a false start or an unfinished sentence.

Hyphen (-)

Used for hyphenated compounds, not for marking stutters (those are normally smoothed away in Clean Read).

Parentheses ()

Reserved for suspected utterances when a word is uncertain, for example:

- (word?)

Transcription tags and timestamps

When using tags, relevance and context are always taken into account. Tags (everything in square brackets) are written in lower case.

Typical mappings:

- Non-verbal affirmative sounds (e.g. *mm-hmm*), when functioning as answers to direct questions:
→ **Yes**
- Non-verbal negative sounds (e.g. *mm-mm*), when functioning as answers to direct questions:
→ **No**
- Incomprehensible passages (after several careful listening attempts, including higher volume and slower playback such as 0.7 speed):
→ [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Context-relevant pauses of approx. 5 seconds or more:
→ [silence 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Crosstalk that leads to incomprehensible passages:
→ [inaudible 00:00:00-00:00:05]
- Foreign-language sections:
→ [foreign language 00:00:00-00:00:05]

Timestamp rules

- As a general principle, only one timestamp per tag type is used per minute.
 - The first occurrence within a minute carries the tag plus timestamp.
 - Subsequent occurrences of the same tag type within that minute are normally marked with the tag only, unless the passage is long enough to justify start and end times.
- Any tag of **5 seconds or longer** is marked with start and end times, regardless of where in the minute it occurs.
- Tags of **4 seconds or less** within the same minute normally do not carry a timestamp if a timestamp has already been given for that tag type in that minute.

Example:

He said [inaudible 00:00:05-00:00:15], but then [silence 00:00:20-00:00:26] I was [foreign language]. Yes, [silence 00:00:30-00:00:36] it was not [inaudible] because we [inaudible].